

STUDENT PROFESSIONAL SKILL EMPOWERMENT THROUGH RESEARCH BASED PEDAGOGICAL TOOLS

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Abstract:

Professional skill development among students is need of hour. Traditional methods of education were not enough to meet professional requirements. There is a huge gap between professional requirement and academia. Majority of degree holder students which came from traditional education system were found unemployable. To sustain in the world professional skills must be developed among students. Problem solving and task-oriented skills are must in today's world. Environmental, economic, project management attitude for business planned must be developed among student.

RBPTs are pedagogical tools that involves recognize, require, refine, reward and report research activity. RBPTs is a step into the unknown, not just remembrance. RBPTs help students to refine their research skills in technical, cognitive & personal way. Role of a teacher in this activity is mentor. Student will excel through by the process of experiential learning. Environmental, economic and project management attitude developed among student. Curiosity about applicability of domain knowledge in practical world is enhanced. RBPT helps student to get research experience and empower themselves with professional skills along with acquisition of domain knowledge. RBPT is a win-win method to student-teacher-institute and society.

Key words: Skill, Learning, Pedagogy, Knowledge, Problem Solving.

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Importance of Skill Based Education:

Teachers and students focus to complete their syllabus framed by syllabus framing bodies. Traditional method of education involves lectures and examinations [1] Many degree holder students were found to be unemployable [2, 3]. Traditional teaching-learning method does not meet the aim and expectation required for professional skills. There is a huge gap between professional skill requirement and academia. So role of teachers and educational institutes should be enhanced. [4,5]

To sustain in the professional world, professional skills must be developed among students. Professional skill based education is need of hour. Environmental, economic, project management attitude for project or business planned must be developed among student. Interdisciplinary study is also required in practical life [6]. For professional success development of research attitude is must. [7]

Introduction To RBPT:

RBPT is pedagogical tool not a research which focuses mainly on incorporating the professional research skills among students. It involves 5R's, namely recognize, require, refine, reward and report research activity. There is no need to disturb framed curriculum. RBPTs is a step into the unknown, not just remembrance. Students excel in study as well as in future careers so the quality of higher education will be enhanced. Students will get research experience, exposure to professional skills required along with acquisition of domain knowledge.

Research Based Pedagogical helps to develop student's research aptitude. This tool is not to be implemented for all the syllabus points rather implemented in one or two concepts individually or in groups. Students enjoys the process of learning by doing and feels empowered for future challenges during profession. Learning by doing is uniqueness of this activity which enhances interest in learning, this is the driving force for student's overall development. Problem solving skills, curiosity and task-oriented thinking ability found to be developed among students. RBPTs help students to refine their research skills in cognitive, technical and personal way and to refine their understanding to build resilient, powerful and predictive understanding.

Role of Mentor Teacher:

The teacher's role in this activity is of a mentor. Mentor teacher prepares brief literature survey and prepares context, problems to be focused on – local or societal problem may be taken as study topic, decide activity to be perform, way in which study should be done,

how results need to be obtained and presented, ways to assess results. Mentor teachers need to work on each student or group of students, keeping blue print of framed PO's and CO's of the curriculum. The activities to be framed so as to develop interdisciplinary learning, project management and execution temperament. Mentor teacher will provide required resources. Students will do brief updated study of the concept under the guidance of mentor teacher. Guidance is only given after inquiry. Students themselves learn new skills such as how to find, read & use literature, finding requirements and their availability and interpretation of results. They can decide on their own convenient methods for carrying out project and plan for execution ideas.

Significance of RBPT:

RBPT is a win-win method to student-teacher -institute and society. Students will learn new skills, get trained, better opportunities for higher studies. Faculty may get publications, helpful for their promotions and taking their research interests forward. Institute will win societal recognition, reputation, better admissions which are helpful during accreditation. Society gains knowledge and possible solutions to local problems. Referencing, procedure, conduction, data collection, presentation and assessment skills get developed. This will help them in their future career.

Evidence of success:

The evidence of success is seen in students working pattern. The students feel confident to do referencing through research books and research articles. Students themselves identify requirements, plan for conducting research or project or business & its monitoring. Students try to find out requirements and availability of sources, result interpretation presentation and arriving at the conclusion and take decision on their own. Students awareness with respect to environmental, economic, management point of view will be built up. Students can excel in their professional career which reflects through their professional achievements. Student's communication and connectivity with faculty will simultaneously enhance the institute.

Challenges encountered and overcome strategies:

- a) **Communication fear among students:** Students with rural background generally have fear to ask doubts, and to communicate for their requirements. They follow the teacher guidelines as stated, but do not clarify the doubt in their mind. This is one of the main hurdles.

- b) **Literature survey:** The institutions does not have facilities like research institutes and industry those are must for profession. This is somewhat overcome by library N-List INFLIBNET access, Open Access Journals, other free tools such as Google Scholar and good communication with subject experts.
- c) **Skills required for understanding language of reference and research articles:** The ability to read, understand and find out correct procedure is hidden skill not developed by traditional practical method.
- d) **Availability of laboratories, materials and facilities:** The advancement in the educational institute classroom and laboratories is somewhat slow as per speed of development in research and also to make available them for extended hours.

Conclusion:

RBPTs is a step into the unknown, not just remembrance. RBPT teaching technique enable students in referencing, planning of project or business, implementation, data collection, interpretation and presentation skills. This technique makes students professionally skilled. Process of learning by doing is achieved as they learn new skills in their personal involvement method. The approach of student for study is revolutionized and meets to standard required in the professional world. Problem solving and task-oriented thinking ability developed among students. RBPTs help students to refine their research skills in cognitive, technical & personal way. RBPT is a win-win method to student-teacher -institute and society.

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